

MECHANISMS OF DEVELOPING THE PEDAGOGICAL THINKING OF FUTURE TEACHERS USING THE QUASI RESEARCH METHOD

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Abstract: This article examines the quasi-professional activity organized within the framework of contextual education as an opportunity to form the professional-pedagogical thinking of future teachers. The role of quasi-professional activity in the step-by-step transition of future teachers to professional activity was demonstrated.

Key words: quasi-method, professional activity, competence, specialist, pedagogical practice, design method, practical project.

Introduction:

One of the priority directions of training future specialists for professional pedagogical activity is to form a competitive staff that incorporates all competencies. Knowledge by itself does not serve to prepare a specialist for professional activity, to set goals and tasks of the educational process, to design one's activities, to start research on the topic, to think creatively and to achieve the expected result.

The organized educational process related to gaining the volume of knowledge is not enough to plan and organize the independent professional activity of the future specialist. These shortcomings create difficulties for the future biology teachers to properly establish and develop their professional activities. From this point of view, in the preparation of future biology teachers for professional activities, they have the ability to properly organize their activities, design, independently set goals and tasks, develop and make decisions related to the management of the educational process. requires being. Therefore, it is important for students not only to acquire the ability to effectively apply this knowledge in the educational process of a higher educational institution, but also to learn how to use it in their future professional activities. For this, future biology teachers should have the opportunity to try themselves as teachers. He is the organizer of research activities of teachers-students. For this purpose, pedagogical practice of students in the undergraduate program is planned.

Pedagogical practice involves preparing students for the process of educational and professional activity at school. This process is a type of activity related to the interaction of future biology teachers with students, their education and upbringing. This requires sufficient knowledge and skills necessary to create favorable psycho-pedagogical conditions for the education and development of children. Quasi-professional activity is a necessary stage of transition from educational activities to the world of professional culture. At this stage, the subject (*mastery of knowledge, skills and experience of professional activity using the system of educational tasks, models and situations*), social (*interaction of participants of the educational process in accordance with accepted social norms*) relational and psychological (*orientation to the profession as a part of culture; through the assimilation of its norms, rules, values*) contexts,

as a result of which the human world consists of value-semantic components of the future professional image. The essence of this activity is that it is carried out in real conditions and ensures the unity of the above contexts.

Quasi-professional activity is one of the forms of contextual education, which involves modeling a certain segment of professional activity, creating real pedagogical situations. By participating in quasi-professional activities, students learn to solve various professional problems, establish a system of pedagogical interactions, and independently solve various problematic situations. In addition, this type of activity can be considered as a kind of transitional period between educational activity and educational and professional activity. This increases the level of preparation of students for teaching practice and solves the problem of fear of expressing one's opinion in public and showing professional knowledge. According to A.A. Verbitsky, this activity is a transition from academic learning activity to educational and professional activity. Students do not perform professional activities, but imitate them. The student accumulates experience in using educational information as a means of activity, increasingly acquires the characteristics of a specialist, which translates the objective meanings of this information into personal meanings, that is, knowledge as a personal property of the future specialist. ensures that it becomes his professional competence.

Quasi-professional activity allows students to acquire and update professional knowledge and competencies, contributes to the formation of meaning-forming professional motives, the development of important professional qualities and thinking, gaining experience in the implementation of knowledge, as well as emotional and voluntary regulation. According to O.B. Dautov, the forms of quasi-professional activity can be:

- 1) design method;**
- 2) situation creation and resolution;**
- 3) organizational-active games;**
- 4) research work of students.**

A design method with rich creative value is *"one of the examples of pedagogical technology, which means a systematic collection and order of operation of all personal, instrumental and methodological technologies used to achieve pedagogical goals."* Design activities are carried out not only by students, but also by teachers. In fact, all the work of a teacher is daily design. Our work has a clear purpose. We set goals and tasks, search for information, process it, and present the results to the public. Therefore, in modern language, the lesson plan is mainly called *"lesson project"*. A project is a set of actions specially organized by a teacher and performed independently by students, ending in the creation of a creative product. Students working on projects:

- ❖ individually or in a group, identifies current issues in life, problems in various fields of knowledge;
- ❖ determines the tasks, creates a work plan, thereby looking for ways to solve the problem, identifies the object of research;
- ❖ puts forward hypotheses, conducts experiments with natural objects, systematizes the received information, analyzes information received from various sources and draws conclusions. In conclusion, the teacher should help students process experimental data, document the results and, of course, develop the ability to cooperate;

- ❖ creates a system of logical arguments, prepares project defense with the help of computer, multimedia equipment;
- ❖ in the presentation of the project, the student presents the result of his work, conveys the issue to the public, shows the solutions to solve these problems. In this process, the development of students' skills of mastering the art of speech and culture is achieved.

Design technology depends on the age and individual characteristics of students and teaches independence and the need for self-awareness. Projects can be classified according to the strengths of students in their work as follows:

- Practical projects: this is aimed at the social interests of the project participants or the external customer. In this case, the product is predetermined and used in a specific activity.
- Research projects: this project is structured like a real scientific research, based on the relevance of the chosen topic, defines the research objectives, necessarily puts forward the hypothesis with confirmation and discusses the obtained results.
- Informative project: in which the student analyzes the object, phenomenon, summarizes and collects information to present to a wide audience.
- Creative projects: in this, the student takes into account a free and unconventional approach to the presentation of project results. These can be almanacs, theatrical performances, sports games, works of visual or decorative art, video films.
- Role projects: In these projects, the structure is not defined and the work is open until completion. Project participants perform specific roles. According to the roles, their tasks are determined.

According to the plot of the game, they should perform roles, in appropriate cases, enter into communication as an "official", and mobilize their existing abilities and talents, acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications. In order to achieve the desired result in the process of solving the project, they need to work hard, search, think independently and creatively, independence and awareness. There is creative exploration here, but it is considered a role-playing project because the project is solved by having the students take on certain roles. Working on projects can be individual, but is often more productive when done in a group. Group projects are of great importance in the formation of students' basic competencies: they develop the ability to work with a team, analyze the situation, and make decisions.

From experience, it is worth noting that the most difficult process is the organization of the initial stage of work on the project. Sometimes it is difficult to choose a topic: after all, it is necessary to take into account the interests of students and the relevance of the issue. Let's say the topic is defined. Now you need to divide the roles in the group: choose a student who will collect theoretical materials, analyze them, prepare a literature review on the topic. Together with other students, it is necessary to carry out the practical part of the research, i.e.: conduct experiments to describe the analyzed material, take photographs or video films, and work on other similar processes. Later, active preparation for the presentation of the research project at the university and then at the regional conference begins. A report is prepared, as a rule, all members or students of a non-state educational institution participate in its preparation. The main author of the research paper presents the draft of the lecture in the traditional way, and then the presentation is discussed and its shortcomings are considered and corrected. The main purpose of pre-listening to the presentation is to form the speaker to be able to answer them without difficulty even when unexpected and thoughtful questions are

asked. Together, students make a plan to answer all the questions. Why should research be discussed in advance? The truth is that students feel anxious when defending a project publicly. As a result, there are cases of excitement, inability to concentrate, and inability to express one's thoughts in front of the observers. During the initial listening process, the student gathers experience of behaving in front of the audience, learns to answer questions correctly, in a word, has the experience of giving a speech and holding a discussion.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, it can be said that every student should have the opportunity to increase his creative potential, to express himself in professional activities, taking into account individual abilities and inclinations. In this case, the design method of quasi-professional activities allows the exchange of experience between the teacher and the student, team work, the formation of speech culture, and mastering the methods of conveying one's knowledge to the listener in a clear and understandable way.

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